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DEVELOPMENT AND SIMULATION OF LEARNING-BASED APPROACH

ENHANCING USER EXPERIENCE BY SUPPORTING DOMAIN KNOWLEDGE DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

In various contexts of interaction, users should creatively adjust their product/system use for fully attaining their goals and ensuring satisfactory experiences. To do so, users need to learn how to apply their problem-solving knowledge in the task domain (i.e. domain knowledge). This research aims to develop a methodology for designing interactive products/systems that can help users actively develop their domain knowledge through interaction. This new approach to interactive product/system design is named Learning-Based Approach (LBA). In order to develop the LBA methodology, this paper first proposes a model of users' knowledge development cycles in interaction. Then, some principles for enhancing the learning cycles are introduced, consisting of principles for motivation, knowledge acquisition, and meta-knowledge acquisition. In final, this paper describes the processes of the development and evaluation of the LBA-based prototype as a case product (a digital camera).

Keywords: Users' domain knowledge, Learning-Based Approach, Interaction design methodology

INTRODUCTION

Technological aids provided by interactive products and systems have reduced people's problem-solving efforts in everyday practices. In order to improve user-product interaction, designers have primarily been concerned with how to help users solve problems and achieve goals more easily and efficiently. Although users' sufficient acquisition of

knowledge for operating a product or system (i.e. operation knowledge) is considered important, their acquisition of problem-solving knowledge in the task domain (i.e. domain knowledge) has largely been disregarded. As a result, domain knowledge has been hidden behind knowledge for operating a product/system, and users' learning of domain problem-solving mechanisms tends to be detached from user experiences.

In the previously-conducted observational research on digital camera and coffee maker use, the authors found that people's domain knowledge (e.g., principles for making delicious coffee) was critical to the effective and satisfactory use of the products. For example, users who were familiar with machine operational procedures (e.g., button/menu steps for operating a coffee maker), but not with coffee-making principles, could not make satisfactory coffee when an unusual situation occurred, and could not utilize the full capability of the coffee maker. In other words, without sufficient domain knowledge, users will not be able to creatively adjust their product/system use in order to achieve satisfactory results and generate better experiences in various contexts of use. Therefore, products/systems should be designed to support users' development of domain problem-solving abilities through interaction.

This research, therefore, aims to develop a methodology for designing interactive products/systems that can help users actively

develop their domain knowledge through interaction. This new approach, named the Learning-Based Approach (LBA), assumes the significance of users' domain knowledge in order to produce high-quality results and ensure higher-level satisfaction. In order to develop the LBA methodology, this paper first proposes a model of users' knowledge development cycle in user-product interaction. Then, some principles for supporting and maintaining the cycles are suggested, based on existing theories and observation results from the previous user study. In order to simulate the principles by designing an example product, the latter part of this paper introduces the development of a digital camera UI (user interface) design. Finally, the new design is evaluated in user tests.

This research is expected to contribute to the product/system design fields two different ways. First, this research calls for designers' attention to the significance of users' domain knowledge. This new approach will be able to provide users with more robust support in achieving their goals; when gaining enough domain problem-solving knowledge through interaction, users will be able to flexibly and creatively utilize the product in order to meet their variable needs. Second, this research also provides designers with applicable methods for employing the proposed approach in their design practices.

KNOWLEDGE DEVELOPMENT IN INTERACTION

KNOWLEDGE INVOLVED IN PRODUCT USE

Knowledge involved in user-product interaction can be classified into two types: knowledge of how to operate a system (i.e. operation knowledge) and knowledge of how to achieve goals in a task domain (i.e. domain knowledge) (Choi & Sato 2009). Domain knowledge not only includes concepts, action sequences, and cause-effect relationships, but also includes any kind of knowledge related to the processes and methods for achieving goals in the domain.

In the product/system design fields, there have been several different approaches to support users' knowledge process in interaction, including considerations of learnability as a usability issue (e.g. Nielsen, 1994) and user support tools such as help

systems and user's manuals (e.g. Carroll, 1990). Most of these approaches tend to be focused only on fast development of users' operation knowledge, largely disregarding users' domain knowledge acquisition. In other words, the main regard in those approaches is to make users become proficient in operating the interface elements (such as menus or buttons) of a product/system.

However, as some researchers points out (e.g. Kaptelinin, 2001), people's primary goal of using a product/system may not be to operate it itself. Rather, they use a product to fulfill certain motivation of their everyday and/or work activities, which is beyond product operation itself.

As mentioned above, this research conducted observational user studies in the previous research phase in order to investigate the effects of users' domain and operation knowledge. The observation results showed that users' sufficient domain knowledge was critical for their higher-level performance and satisfaction; in order to achieve goals, users should be able to effectively apply both types of knowledge to their interaction with a product/system. Therefore, it is not sufficient for designers to consider how to support users' efficient operation knowledge acquisition. Rather, designers also need to consider how to make users' domain knowledge development become a part of their product use experience.

USERS' LEARNING CYCLE IN INTERACTION

In order to employ users' domain knowledge into design practice, which is named the Learning-Based Approach, this paper first proposes a model of users' knowledge development cycles in using a product, as shown in Figure 1. This model is developed by adapting Norman (1988)'s model of cognitive actions in user-product interaction. Norman's model effectively explains the cognitive processes involved in goal-driven actions when users interact with a product. Since Norman's model tends to focus on user's and system's cognitive *actions*, this research tries to expand the scope of users' goal-driven actions in Norman's original model in order to include users' activities driven by higher-level motivation. According to Leont'ev (1978), there is a three-level hierarchy of motivation: motive-driven activity, goal-driven action, and operations driven by

the tools and conditions of actions. The primary purpose of users' product use may be to fulfill motive-level motivation, rather than successful execution of actions.

Figure 1. Users' cognitive processes in learning through interaction

Figure 1 describes users' motive-driven cognitive processes in product use, involving various factors of the cycle and relations among the factors. Figure 1 also shows the significant roles of users' domain knowledge in maintaining the cycle of interaction and learning. Some steps of the cycle as follows.

- *Motivations shaped in a domain:* What kinds of motivations a user has is one of the most critical factors of the consequent learning processes because motivations not only guide the initiation of actions, but also guide the direction of the actions and the amount of effort given to the actions (Keller, 1987). Initially, internal and external factors arouse a user's motivations for knowledge development.
- *Formation of goals:* Once a user has need for more knowledge, he/she forms action goals in order to obtain necessary knowledge by using a product (e.g. making a cup of delicious coffee by using a coffee maker).
- *Construction of expectations:* Based on their existing domain and operational knowledge, users

then build up certain expectations for the resulting quality (quality of coffee) and the product's actions.

- *Plan action sequences:* Users' existing knowledge levels also affect whether they can set up an effective plan for action sequences in order to successfully manipulate problem-solving mechanisms by operating a product (e.g. what to do using a coffee maker to make delicious coffee).
- *Execution of actions:* Users execute actions according to their action plan.
- *Perception of outcomes:* After executing a series of actions, the user will perceive the outcomes, which includes the results of interaction (e.g. taste and smell of resulting coffee) as well as product feedback (i.e. any kinds of product's responses to a user's actions, such as feedback on the screen).
- *Interpretation of outcomes:* Users then attempts to interpret the perceived consequences, based on their knowledge.
- *Evaluation of performance and experiences:* By comparing the interpretations to initial expectations, users may assess their performance in terms of the quality of results (e.g. whether the quality of resulting coffee is the same as a user expected / desired), product operations (e.g. whether the machine's responses are the same as expected), and overall experiences (e.g. how enjoyable the coffee-making processes were).
- *Assessment of satisfaction:* The criteria for assessing satisfaction are drawn from the user's own needs shaped in the domain. If the users are not satisfied with either the quality of results or their experiences in the goal-achieving processes, or is dissatisfied with both, they may want to improve the current state by acquiring further knowledge. Users may, however, choose to cease learning if the quality of results and their experiences are completely satisfactory (e.g. a user reaches a desired quality of coffee and has a satisfactory experience).
- *Assessment of causes and values:* If unsatisfied with the current results, a user may want to infer the causes of failures, which can be called causal attribution. According to Driscoll (2005), causal attribution which refers to "what attributions people are making about their failure and success in learning" (p. 323) is an important factor for understanding people's continuing motivation to

knowledge acquisition. Weiner (1985) postulates three dimensions of causal attributions: internal versus external causes, stable versus unstable causes, and controllable causes versus uncontrollable causes. For example, if the user thinks that the cause of failure is his/her insufficient ability, and considers the cause to be internal, but stable and uncontrollable, he/she may stop further learning (i.e. continuing use). On the other hand, if the user considers insufficient ability to be internal, unstable, and controllable, then he/she may want to keep learning.

- *Assessment of values:* Because learning is supposed to require a certain amount of effort, a user may determine whether knowledge development is worth undertaking, which is value assessment. Although a user thinks that he/she can improve the current quality of results and of their experiences by obtaining more knowledge and skills, the user may not sustain learning if the improved quality does not deserve to be achieved.

In sum, in order to maintain this cycle (that is, to continuously motivate and support users' learning in product use), designers should consider several important factors of learning cycles; 1) how to sustain users' motivations by reducing obstacles to their continuous learning, 2) how to provide necessary knowledge for users in order to help them effectively build up expectations and conduct comparative expectation-result assessment, and 3) how to provide users with feeling of control in the processes of their knowledge development for using a product as well as producing quality results. Based on these categories, some specific principles for enhancing users' learning are described in the next section.

PRINCIPLES OF LEARNING-BASED APPROACH (LBA)

Considering the significant roles of domain knowledge in product/system use, this research proposes a new approach to interactive product/system design: the Learning-Based Approach (LBA). A central idea of this approach is that domain knowledge should be properly incorporated into product design processes. In design processes, designers should consider how to embed domain knowledge into a product and effectively represent

it in forms of user interface designs, so that users can continuously obtain domain knowledge through their interaction with a product/system.

Based on the factors of learning as identified in the learning cycle model as well as findings from previously-conducted user studies, this research proposes specific principles for enhancing users' learning in interaction. The summary of the proposed principles are summarized as Table 1.

As previously mentioned, the LBA principles are divided into three categories: principles for motivating users' learning, for supporting knowledge acquisition, and for supporting meta-knowledge acquisition.

PRINCIPLES FOR MOTIVATING USERS' LEARNING

Users' learning through product use is highly self-motivated, and its initiation and cessation are mostly dependent upon users' needs and propensity for learning. When referring to the model of users' learning cycles depicted in Figure 1, it can be said that users' continuous knowledge development occurs when several conditions are met: 1) users are dissatisfied with the current quality of results and/or experiences, that is, they feel there may be the potential for better quality, 2) they suppose that they can improve the current quality, and 3) they determine that the improved quality would be worth their effort of learning. Therefore, principles for motivating users' continual development of knowledge should effectively address these three conditions in learning cycles.

Keller (1987) postulates that people's learning processes can be improved by effectively planning several motivational factors of learning events. By slightly modifying Keller's categories, this research describes four factors of motivations for users' learning: attention, relevance, confidence, and reward.

- **Attention.** In order to initiate and sustain users' learning, it is necessary to gain and maintain their attention to the learning events. One of the typical methods for attracting people's attention to certain information is to provide novel, uncertain, incongruous, or surprising stimuli, which is named the "perceptual arousal" approach by Keller (1987). Also, in order to encourage users' more lasting

Categories	Factors	Parameters	Principles
Principles for motivating users' learning	Attention	- Perceptual arousal	- Increase participation in learning by attracting users' perceptual attention
		- Inquiry arousal	- Stimulate users' intellectual curiosity by presenting them with challenging, but interesting problems-solving situations
	Relevance	- Matching to goals/interests	- Provide knowledge that is related to the user's goals and interests during system use
		- Familiarity	- Provide knowledge in a manner that matches the users' contextual conditions
	Confidence	- Expectedness	- Help users create appropriate expectations of the improvement of results quality with relation to their learning - Demonstrate what kinds of output quality would be possible by using the system - Design user interfaces by which users can predict system feedback
		- Feeling of self-efficacy	- Help users have a feeling of self-efficacy through their knowledge acquisition and transfer processes
	Reward	- Intrinsic reward	- Provide opportunities for users to appreciate their improvement of results
		- Extrinsic reward	- Provide mechanisms for users to share their results and receive other people's feedback
Principles for supporting users' knowledge acquisition	Availability of knowledge	- Sufficiency	- Help users obtain enough knowledge for desired quality outcomes
		- Sources	- Inform users of and increase the accessibility to different sources of available knowledge - Deliver knowledge in a way that allows users to obtain knowledge in their regular processes of system use
		- Timeliness	- Help users obtain knowledge as and when needed
	Types of knowledge	- Operation kn.	- Support users' acquisition of operation knowledge
		- Domain kn.	- Support users' acquisition of domain knowledge
	Appropriateness of knowledge	- Level of knowledge	- Provide levels of knowledge appropriate to users' existing knowledge
		- Context matching	- Provide knowledge needed in or matched with users' particular contexts
		- Internal representation	- Visualize information in such a way that users can build appropriate internal representations (mental models)
		- External representation	- Create user interface designs that fit with users' existing mental models
	Principles for supporting meta-knowledge acquisition	Visibility of learning processes	- Self-monitoring
- Self-evaluation			- Provide mechanisms by which users can evaluate their performance in learning processes
Manipulability of learning processes		- Planning	- Clarify the future steps by which users can obtain necessary knowledge to achieve goals
		- Transferability	- Support users' transfer of existing knowledge to relevant problem-solving
		- Customizability	- Allow users to adjust their knowledge acquisition and utilization processes to their needs and preferences

Table1. Principles for enhancing users' learning in interaction

engagement with their self-directed learning, an effective strategy can be to invoke their intellectual curiosity by involving them in challenging, but interesting problem-solving situations - named "inquiry arousal" (Keller, 1987).

- **Relevance.** When users think that their learning processes are closely related to their personal interests or goals, they may be more actively

engaged in knowledge development when using a product. In order to increase such interest in learning, applicable principles can include providing knowledge that is related to people's goals or interests, and providing knowledge in such a way that users feel familiar with the knowledge (Keller, 1987).

- **Confidence.** This research also suggests that users' motivations for further learning can be increased as they have more confidence and self-efficacy in their learning processes during product use. For example, Driscoll (2005) argues that an important factor in people's continuing motivations for learning is whether the consequences of learning meet their expectations, giving them a feeling of self-efficacy in learning events. As users have more opportunities to experience *expected* successes through *active* knowledge development in interaction, they will become more amenable to further knowledge development.

- **Reward.** In the Figure 1, an important factor for sustaining a user's learning when using a product is whether the user thinks the learning outcomes are worth achieving, compared to his/her efforts to learn. In order to stimulate people's motivations to learn, Keller (1987) suggests using two kinds of rewards: intrinsic and extrinsic. The strategy of *intrinsic* rewards includes supporting enjoyment of learning experiences and providing opportunities to apply new knowledge in order to produce better results. On the other hand, the strategy of *extrinsic* rewards includes providing opportunities for receiving positive and motivational feedback from the environment (e.g. other people's praise).

PRINCIPLES FOR SUPPORTING KNOWLEDGE ACQUISITION

In order to support users' knowledge development through interaction with a product, it is essential for designers to consider how to effectively support users' acquisition of knowledge, which is necessary to achieve goals. As was described in Figure 1, users' adequate and appropriate knowledge-levels are crucial for their creation of adequate expectations and interpretations, as well as for choosing proper actions. Many of the problems observed in participants' learning processes during product use were considered to be related to inappropriate support for factors such as availability, types, appropriateness, and representation of knowledge.

- **Availability of knowledge.** Designers should consider designing a product that can help users obtain necessary knowledge through their regular task-performing processes. In addition, since users'

learning through product interaction is thought of as incidentally occurring during any moments of their problem-solving situations, it is important to support users' efficient knowledge acquisition at the time when they need the knowledge immediately.

In order to support users' acquisition of knowledge that are distributed in external sources, product designs need to help users not only with identifying where and how they can find and obtain knowledge necessary to achieve their goals, but also with efficiently accessing particular knowledge sources.

- **Types of knowledge.** Based on the theoretical and empirical investigations in this study, it is clear that users can produce quality results and develop their problem-solving abilities by applying both domain and operation knowledge. Therefore, when designers seek to support users' knowledge acquisition in interaction with a product, they should consider supporting users' acquisition of both types of knowledge through product interaction.

- **Appropriateness of knowledge.** From the findings from previous user studies, users' performance and experiences with their problem-solving varied according to their levels of goals and expectations, existing knowledge, and personal preferences in learning. In order to augment the effectiveness of people's learning, recent research in the field of instructional system design increasingly focuses on how to choose and deliver knowledge in a way that is adapted to individual learners' goals, knowledge, and other contextual conditions by developing proper learner models (e.g. Weber, 1999). Similarly, users' learning processes in product use can be more effectively supported by providing users with context-matching and appropriate levels of knowledge.

- **Representation of knowledge.** In order to enhance users' acquisition of knowledge in product use, domain and operational knowledge should be represented via interface designs in a way that representations can fit with users' existing internal models, thereby supporting their learning processes. In the UI design field, representations of information or knowledge have been thought of as a crucial factor for users' effective knowledge process during product use. Some researchers are concerned with the influences of a product's external representations of knowledge, and these researchers

argue that in order for users to more efficiently learn the product operations, user interfaces must be designed to assist in constructing productive internal representations (i.e. mental models) of relevant aspects of the product (Preece et al., 1994). Some other researchers focus more on the interwoven relationships between external and internal representations, and assert that external representations of knowledge delivered by a product should be matched with users' internal representations (i.e. mental models) in order to improve the quality of users' interaction with a product/system (Zhang, 1993; Norman, 1993).

PRINCIPLES FOR SUPPORTING KMETA-KNOWLEDGE ACQUISITION

Designers should consider helping users to learn how to actively control their product use and learning processes, which can be called the acquisition of meta-knowledge. Meta-knowledge is generally defined as "knowledge about knowledge" (Pitrat, 1991). In other words, people who have abilities to effectively use their meta-knowledge are aware of what they know or do not know, they can predict outcomes of performance, plan efficient processes for the performance, and monitor the problem-solving outcomes and/or attempts to learn (Gagné & Glaser, 1987). Zimmerman and Schunk (2008) also emphasize that people's "self-observation" and "self-control" play important roles in their self-regulated knowledge development processes. Table 1 describes two categories of principles for supporting users' development of meta-knowledge, by which two main aspects of meta-knowledge - self-observation and self-control - can be supported.

- **Visibility of learning processes.** Norman (1988) insists on visibility as one of the key principles that interactive product/system designs should meet in order to support users' cognitive processes in communicating with a product/system. The principle of visibility is concerned with whether the users can see the state of the product and the alternatives for their actions. In the present research, this principle can be more specifically adapted for explaining users' knowledge-generating processes: in order to support users' knowledge development, products should allow them to see the state of their learning

processes and the alternative for better learning. In particular, since users' assessments of the quality of results is considered important to their continuous learning processes, products should provide mechanisms by which users can effectively monitor and evaluate the changed or unchanged quality of results, this approach allows users to appropriately modify their knowledge acquisition in the future. In this way, users will be able to experience a feeling of increased control over their knowledge development processes.

- **Manipulability of learning processes.** Visibility of a product/system in terms of users' learning processes can significantly affect the manipulability of the processes. In order to effectively achieve goals by obtaining and applying knowledge through product use, users should be able to manipulate their own knowledge development processes.

Manipulability of learning processes in product use can involve abilities for planning learning processes, transferring the obtained knowledge to new situations, and customizing learning processes in various contexts.

Considering mechanisms for increasing manipulability of knowledge-generating processes is particularly important for supporting users' abilities to creatively adjust their product use to meet their needs in various contexts. Some design researchers argue that while using interface designs, users should be able to see and adjust the mechanisms by which the product infers the contexts and chooses proper actions so that they can create desired outcomes matched to the contexts (e.g. Greenberg, 2001). In order for users to fulfill their various needs, a product should allow users to obtain different kinds of knowledge to achieve the same goal, and/or generate new knowledge in different ways.

The three categories of principles for enhancing users' learning processes are not completely exclusive, rather, are closely interrelated. For example, whether or not users can be empowered to control their knowledge and product use processes (that is, whether products provide users with visibility and manipulability in their learning processes), is closely related to their motivations for continuous learning and product use.

Through the user studies, it was found that users who had enough domain knowledge were able to create more accurate expectations, and consequently, have more confidence in their problem-solving processes. They also tended to care more about improving the quality of results (i.e. coffee taste and photo quality), based on their higher expectations of the resulting quality. From the observations, it is clear that *supporting users' development of domain knowledge* can not only be a useful strategy for providing necessary knowledge for achieving their goals, but also *an effective mechanism for motivating their further knowledge development* by increasing their confidence and sensitivity to improving the quality of results (i.e. intrinsic reward) when using a product/system.

SIMULATION OF THE LBA

This paper introduces the processes of simulation and evaluation of the LBA methodology. The LBA emphasizes that domain knowledge should be appropriately incorporated into product/system designs so that users' development of domain knowledge can be an integral part of their experiences with the products/systems. Therefore, a product developed with the LBA is expected to effectively deliver domain knowledge via its user interface (UI) designs and to support users' constant construction of their own domain knowledge through interaction.

As a case product, a digital camera prototype was developed, employing the proposed LBA principles. For example, the UI of the prototype was designed to continuously inform users of possible better quality photos via the LCD screen in order to increase their constant learning motivation. Also, it provides the exposure-controlling knowledge, which is the key principle of the photo-taking domain. The working prototype was developed using BASIC Stamp II and Macromedia Director on a PC platform. The prototype consists of the physical user interface module (as shown in Figure 2 and 3) and the computer screen simulator (as shown in Figure 4), whose operations immediately respond to the operations of the physical module. The contents of the camera prototype were tuned for novices in the photo-taking domain.

Figure 2. Block diagram of the physical module of the digital camera prototype

Figure 3. Prototype of a LBA-applied product: PUI module (left) and the link between the PUI and GUI modules (right)

Figure 4. Example scenes of the user interface of the prototype

USER TEST FOR EVALUATING THE PROTOTYPE

Some observational user studies were conducted to evaluate the new design prototype, which was developed by employing the Learning-Based Approach. Since the primary purpose of the test was to investigate the effects of domain knowledge embedded in the prototype, this research recruited participants who did not have knowledge of photo-taking principles (i.e., domain novices). In total, seven males and five females participated in the user tests, and their ages ranged from nineteen to forty. In the observation sessions, participants were asked to "take a satisfactory photo of a given painting as though you are in a museum where the use of flash function is not allowed." Before and after the task sessions, pre- and post-observation questionnaires were provided in order to further inquire about the contexts and rationales of their task performance. In order to evaluate the new camera prototype, this research adopts the principles for enhancing users' learning as the evaluation criteria (i.e., principles for supporting motivation, knowledge acquisition, and meta-knowledge acquisition). The collected protocol data were qualitatively analyzed according to the categories of the LBA principles.

The user observation results indicate that participants were satisfied overall with the LBA-applied new camera design: indeed, the LBA concept seemed advantageous for users in terms of its self-motivating and learning-supporting features. For instance, one user reported, "I often get frustrated by the poor quality of the photos I take. Using this prototype, though, I didn't feel as frustrated even when the image on the screen wasn't good because I was able to see what I could do for better quality - I could see that it was possible for me to take a better picture quickly (Principles for supporting meta-knowledge acquisition)." One of the most positive responses participants offered about the prototype concerned the 'graphic + auditory' modality that was used for explaining the aperture and shutter speed control principles because of its easiness to understand.

The user tests not only confirm the positive effects of providing domain knowledge for users, but also provide some useful insights for refining the LBA

methodology. For example, the ON/DN user's complaint regarding the confusion of encountering multiple photographic options together at the same time provides this research with some ideas for improvement: in order to satisfy users who have diverse levels of existing knowledge, the LBA methods need to include more elaborate strategies for planning the order of domain knowledge presentation according to users' particular knowledge levels.

The user test results also suggest that, when designers are concerned with users' motivations for learning and using a product/system, they need to conduct more long-term investigations in users' real contexts of use rather than short-term observations in experimental settings.

CONCLUSIONS

In this research, the Learning-Based Approach (LBA) to interactive product/system design is proposed to provide designers with a new viewpoint of users' knowledge development in interaction, as well as applicable methods for developing a product from this perspective. The LBA methodology emphasizes that product/system designers should consider how to help users develop enough domain knowledge through interaction. By synthesizing the conceptualization of users' knowledge development cycle in interaction and findings from empirical user studies previously conducted, this paper proposes three categories of LBA principles for enhancing users' learning in interaction: principles for motivating learning, supporting knowledge acquisition, and supporting meta-knowledge acquisition. Then, the LBA is applied to developing a working prototype of a digital camera as a case product. Using the prototype, this research conducted user tests in order to evaluate the LBA-applied design, with criteria of the proposed principles. The test results show that participants were satisfied overall with the LBA-applied new camera design; the LBA concept seemed advantageous for users in terms of its self-motivating and learning-supporting features. The user tests also provided some insights for improving the current LBA methods.

In order to develop the proposed approach to become a more generic and robust methodology, the

future studies need to conduct additional multiple times of case studies by using diverse types of products/systems.

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